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THE INFLUENCE OF LEADERSHIP AND SUPERVISION ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE THROUGH MOTIVATION AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE

ВПЛИВ ЛІДЕРСТВА ТА НАГЛЯДУ НА ПРОДУКТИВНІСТЬ ПРАЦІВНИКІВ ЧЕРЕЗ МОТИВАЦІЮ ЯК ПРОМІЖНУ ЗМІННУ

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Хафса Харахан, Роберт Туа Сірегар, Еллі Ромі, Кат Фітрі Ростіна. Вплив лідерства та керівництва на продуктивність працівників через мотивацію як проміжну змінну. Науково-методична стаття.

Це дослідження має на меті оцінити вплив лідерства та нагляду на ефективність роботи через мотивацію як проміжну змінну в поліцейському підрозділі державної служби регентства Лабуханбату. Вибірка дослідження складається з 73 постійних працівників (державних службовців) цього підрозділу. Дані були зібрані за допомогою анкетування та документальних досліджень і проаналізовані за допомогою SPSS версії 25. Результати показують, що лідерство і контроль мають позитивний і значний вплив на мотивацію і продуктивність. Крім того, мотивація також має позитивний і значущий вплив на результативність. Нарешті, лідерство та контроль впливають на результативність через мотивацію як проміжну змінну.

Ключові слова: лідерство, ефективність, мотивація, нагляд

Hafsa Harahap, Robert Tua Siregar, Elly Romy, Cut Fitri Rostina. The Influence of Leadership and Supervision on Employee Performance Through Motivation as an Intervening Variable. Scientific and methodical article.

This study aims to evaluate the influence of Leadership and Supervision on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency. The research sample consists of 73 permanent employees (civil servants) in that unit. Data were collected through questionnaires and documentary studies, and analyzed using SPSS version 25. The results indicate that Leadership and Supervision have a positive and significant influence on Motivation and Performance. Additionally, Motivation also has a positive and significant influence on Performance. Finally, Leadership and Supervision influence Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable.

Keywords: leadership, performance, motivation, supervision

Performance is the tangible behavior exhibited by individuals as the work achievement produced by employees in accordance with their roles in the organization. Employee performance is a crucial aspect within an organization to achieve its goals. In organizational settings, human resource factors represent a primary concern in every activity therein because if the human resources within the organization are deficient, then the organization's goals cannot be achieved as planned. This is because the role of human resources in an organization is determinant of the organization's success. All actions undertaken in every activity are initiated and determined by the individuals who are members of an organization.

Based on Government Regulation No. 6/2010 on the Pamong Praja Police Unit, it is stated that the Pamong Praja Police Unit has the task of enforcing Regional Regulations and organising public order and tranquillity as well as community protection.

Leadership style is a norm of behaviour used by a leader when he/she influences subordinates. A leader can use various methods in influencing and motivating subordinates or other people to take actions that are always directed towards achieving organisational goals. This method reflects the leader's attitude and view of the people he leads and is a description of the leadership style.

Analysis of recent research and publications

Based on Government Regulation Number 6 of 2010 concerning the Civil Service Police Unit, it is stated that the Civil Service Police Unit has the duty to enforce Regional Regulations and carry out public order and tranquility as well as community protection. Leadership style is a norm of behavior used by a leader when influencing his subordinates. A leader can use various methods in activities to influence and motivate subordinates or others to take actions that are always directed towards achieving organizational goals. This method reflects the attitude and views of the leader towards the people he leads and is a depiction of the leadership style. By showing the existence of a good leadership style towards his subordinates, it can influence the level of employee job satisfaction, employee behavior will change according to the changes applied by the leaders (Sarita and Agustia, 2009). Based on the background above, a study titled "The Influence of Leadership and Supervision on Employee Performance Through Motivation as an Intervening Variable in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency" is needed.

The main part

Performance is the outcome of work achieved based on measurable quality and quantity requirements and job rules set within a specific time period, carried out with full responsibility according to procedures and criteria applicable within the organization to achieve the goals set by the organization. The performance assessment indicators are as follows:

1. Quantity of work results.
2. Quality of work results.
3. Efficiency in task execution.
4. Work discipline.
5. Initiative.
6. Precision.
7. Leadership.
8. Honesty.
9. Creativity.

Leadership is the act of directing others by motivating, influencing, and guiding them to work

together and assist each other in completing tasks to achieve goals optimally. The indicators for assessing leadership are:

1. Analytical skills.
2. Exemplary behavior.
3. Rationality and objectivity.
4. Work instructions.
5. Ability to listen to advice.
6. Communication skills.
7. Task allocation.
8. Firmness in action.

Supervision is the process of ensuring, monitoring, and evaluating that activities or actions align with the intended goals. Supervision is crucially important to prevent the occurrence of errors or deviations, and to take corrective actions on these errors or deviations to achieve the goals set by the institution. The indicators in assessing supervision are as follows:

1. Establishing standards.
2. Measurement.
3. Comparison.
4. Taking action.

Motivation is the force or drive within an individual that prompts them to engage in activities or actions to achieve their goals. The indicators to assess motivation are as follows:

1. Physical needs.
2. Safety and security needs.
3. Social needs.
4. Recognition needs.
5. Self-actualization needs.

RESULT This research employs the path analysis model to analyze the influence of leadership and supervision on employee performance through motivation as an intervening variable in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency.

Respondent Characteristics. The majority of respondents were 41-50 years old with 30 employees (53.4%). While the number of respondents aged 20-30 years was 15 employees (27.4%), the number of respondents aged 31-40 was 16 employees (24.7%) and the number of respondents aged > 50 years was 12 employees (19.2%).

Table 1. Results of t-Test for Sub Model I

Coefficients ^a						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	21.492	.876		24.525	.000
	Leadership	.071	.022	.357	3.252	.002
	Supervision	.050	.032	.169	2.544	.027

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation

Source: the authors' own elaboration

In the table, the t-test statistics are obtained as follows:

1. Leadership variable (X1) with a t-value (3.252) > t-table (1.99) at a significance level (Sig) of 0.000

(< 0.05). This indicates that Leadership significantly influences the Motivation variable.

2. Supervision variable (X2) with a t-value (2.544) > t-table (1.99) at a significance level (Sig) of 0.027 (< 0.05). This indicates that Supervision significantly influences the Motivation variable.

Table 2. Summary of Model Testing Results for Sub-Model I

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.397	.158	.134	.436

Source: the authors' own elaboration

The data above indicates that the contribution or influence of the Leadership variable (X1) and Supervision variable (X2) on the Motivation variable (Z) is 13.4%, while the remaining 86.6% is

contributed by other variables not included in the study. Meanwhile, for the value of $\hat{\epsilon}_1$, it can be calculated using the formula $\hat{\epsilon}_1 = \sqrt{1-0.134} = 0.9305$.

Table 3. Results of t-Test for Sub Model II

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	26.501	6.228		4.255	.000
	Leadership	.212	.054	.426	3.930	.000
	Supervision	.288	.076	.391	3.805	.000
	Motivation	.350	.274	.140	2.276	.006

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Source: the authors' own elaboration

In the table, the t-test statistics are obtained as follows:

1. Leadership variable (X1) with a t-value of (3.930) > t-table (1.99) at a significance probability level (Sig) of 0.000 (< 0.05).

2. This indicates that Leadership has a significant influence on the Performance variable. Supervision variable (X2) with a t-value of (3.805) > t-table (1.99)

at a significance probability level (Sig) of 0.000 (< 0.05).

3. This indicates that Supervision has a significant influence on the Performance variable. Motivation variable (Z) with a t-value of (2.276) > t-table (1.99) at a significance probability level (Sig) of 0.006 (< 0.05).

This indicates that Motivation has a significant influence on the Performance variable.

Table 4. Summary of Model Testing Results for Sub-Model II

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.545	.297	.266	1.000

Source: the authors' own elaboration

The data above indicate that the contribution or influence of the variables Leadership (X1), Supervision (X2), and Motivation (Z) on the variable Performance (Y) is 26.6%, while the remaining 73.4% is the contribution from other variables not included in the study. Meanwhile, for the value of $\hat{\epsilon}_1$, it can be calculated using the formula $\hat{\epsilon}_1 = \sqrt{1-0.266} = 0.8567$.

$$Y = 26,501 + 0,212X_1 + 0,288X_2 + 0,350Z$$

The analysis results show that the direct influence provided by Leadership (X1) on Performance (Y) is 0.357. Meanwhile, the indirect influence of Leadership (X1) on Performance (Y) through Motivation (Z) is $0.426 \times 0.140 = 0.059$. Therefore, the total influence provided by the Leadership variable (X1) on Performance (Y) is the sum of the direct and indirect influences, which is $0.357 + 0.059 = 0.416$. Based on the calculation results above, it can be observed that the value of the direct influence is

0.357 and the value of the indirect influence is 0.059, indicating that the direct influence is greater than the indirect influence. This result indicates that indirectly, the Leadership variable (X1) through Motivation (Z) has a significant effect on Performance (Y). The analysis results indicate that the direct influence provided by Supervision (X2) on Performance (Y) is 0.169. Meanwhile, the indirect influence of Supervision (X2) on Performance (Y) through Motivation (Z) is $0.391 \times 0.140 = 0.054$. Therefore, the total influence provided by the Supervision variable (X2) on Performance (Y) is the sum of the direct and indirect influences, which is $0.169 + 0.054 = 0.445$. Based on the calculation results above, it can be observed that the value of the direct influence is 0.169 and the value of the indirect influence is 0.054, indicating that the direct influence is greater than the indirect influence. This result indicates that indirectly, the Supervision variable (X2) through Motivation (Z) has a significant effect on Performance (Y).

Table 5. Results of t-Test for Sub Model II

Variabel	Unstandardized	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Std. Error	P-Value
Leadership on Motivation	0.072 (a)	0.022 (S _a)	0.538	0.021	0.590
Motivation to Performance	0.161 (b)	0.295 (S _b)			
Supervision on Motivation	0.052 (a)	0.035 (S _a)	0.141	0.014	0.887
Motivation to Performance	0.040 (b)	0.281 (S _b)			

Source: the authors' own elaboration

The test statistic value of the influence of Leadership on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable has a test statistic value of 0.538 < 1.96 with significance of 0.590 > 0.05, which means Hypothesis 6 is not accepted where Motivation is unable to mediate the influence of Leadership on Performance. The test statistic value of the influence of Supervision on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable has a test statistic value of 0.141 < 1.96 with significance of 0.887 > 0.05, which means Hypothesis 7 is not accepted where Motivation is unable to mediate the influence of Supervision on Performance.

The Influence of Leadership on Motivation. The Leadership variable has a positive and significant effect on Motivation in the Labuhanbatu Civil Service Police Unit. The Leadership variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.071, indicating that if Leadership increases by 100%, it will increase Motivation by 7.1%.

The influence of supervision on motivation. The Supervision variable has a positive and significant effect on Motivation in the Labuhanbatu Civil Service Police Unit. The Supervision variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.050, indicating that if Supervision increases by 100%, it will increase Motivation by 5%.

The Influence of Leadership on Performance. The leadership variable has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu Civil Service Police Unit. The leadership variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.212, indicating that if leadership increases by 100%, it will increase performance by 21.2%.

The influence of supervision on performance. The Supervision variable has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu Civil Service Police Unit. The Supervision variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.288, indicating that if supervision increases by 100%, it will increase performance by 28.8%.

The influence of motivation on performance. Motivation variable has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu Civil Service Police Unit. The motivation variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.350, indicating that if motivation increases by 100%, it will increase performance by 35%.

The Influence of Leadership on Performance through Motivation. Based on the results of the sobel test calculation, it is known that the test statistic value is 0.538 < 1.96 with a significant value of 0.590 > 0.05, it can be concluded that the Motivation variable is not able to mediate the relationship between the

influence of Leadership on Performance. Thus it can be said that Leadership has no influence in improving Performance if done through Motivation.

The Influence of Supervision on Performance through Motivation. Based on the results of the sobel test calculation, it is known that the test statistic value is 0.141 < 1.96 with a significant value of 0.887 > 0.05, it can be concluded that the Motivation variable is unable to mediate the relationship between the influence of Supervision on Performance. Thus it can be said that Supervision has no influence in improving Performance if done through Motivation.

Conclusions

Based on the research results and discussions conducted by the researcher regarding the influence of Leadership and Supervision on the performance of employees in the Civil Service Police Unit through Motivation as an intervening variable, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Leadership influences Motivation in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency.
2. Supervision influences Motivation in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency.
3. Leadership influences Performance in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency.
4. Supervision influences Performance in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency.
5. Motivation influences Performance in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency.
6. Leadership influences Performance in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency through Motivation as an intervening variable.
7. Supervision influences Performance in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency through Motivation as an intervening variable.

Suggestions.

1. The Labuhanbatu District Civil Service Police Unit should pay attention to the issues faced by employees and find solutions together.
2. The Labuhanbatu District Civil Service Police Unit should pay attention to and develop each work program with well-structured and conceptualized steps, as well as create detailed and easily understandable steps and instructions for employees.
3. The Labuhanbatu District Civil Service Police Unit should pay attention to employees in case of deviations and correct or rectify any mistakes that occur.
4. The Labuhanbatu District Civil Service Police Unit should pay attention to employees who have job achievement targets so that they have benchmarks for the results they intend to achieve.
5. The Labuhanbatu District Civil Service Police Unit should pay attention to each group in the

completion of work issues being resolved in groups so that employees feel loved, loved, and have harmonious relationships with their colleagues.

6. The Labuhanbatu District Civil Service Police Unit should pay attention to social security guarantees for labor, pension funds, and health insurance.

Abstract

This study aims to determine whether Leadership and Supervision affect Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable in employees of the Labuhanbatu Regency Pamong Praja Police Unit. The research was conducted on permanent employees (PNS) at the Labuhanbatu Regency Pamong Praja Police Unit. The population in this study was 73 people. Due to the small population, the sampling technique in this study was a saturated sample with a sample size of 73 people. The data collection techniques used are primary data in the form of questionnaires and secondary data obtained through documentation studies. The data analysis technique uses quantitative data processed with the SPSS version 25 program, namely the t test, sobel test and path analysis. The results obtained in this study indicate 1) there is a positive and significant influence between Leadership on Motivation, 2) there is a positive and significant influence between Supervision on Motivation, 3) there is a positive and significant influence between Leadership variables on Performance, 4) there is a positive and significant influence between Supervision on Performance, 5) there is a positive and significant influence between Motivation on Performance, 6) There is an influence ... between Leadership on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable, 7). There is an influence ... between Supervision on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable.

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